

“Methodology Pre-validation Report”

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15.07.2024	<i>final version resubmitted to Participant Portal following General Project Review Consolidated Report (HE)</i>	V2.1

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia-Collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. Its aim is to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until the end of the project, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1,000 companies, 3,000 students and 300 researchers by project end. INDUSAC counts on a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that provides the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

D1.5 Methodology Pre-validation Report describes major questions, comments, and recommendations based on the two-hour virtual workshop that took place on 15 September 2023. During the workshop, participants - students, researchers, and representatives of companies - were introduced to the INDUSAC project methodology and a simulation of the INDUSAC platform, and were given the opportunity to ask questions and post comments via Miro board, prompting real-time discussion during the workshop. The feedback will serve as a guide to improve the beta version of the methodology. The collected questions will also be used to populate the Frequently-Asked-Question section on the INDUSAC website.

Keywords: INDUSAC, academia-industry cooperation, methodology, INDUSAC platform, co-creation

LIST OF ACRONYMS

BAX	Bax Innovation Consulting SL
D	Deliverable
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
EU	European Union
FAQ	Frequently asked questions
IAC	INDUSty-Academia-Collaboration
ID	Identification
INDUSAC	Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia-Collaborations
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Community
PCA	Pre-defined Collaborative Approach
PPT	PowerPoint
WP	Work Package

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I. INTRODUCTION

D1.5 Methodology Pre-validation Report describes major questions, comments, and recommendations based on the two-hour virtual workshop that took place on 15 September 2023. The goals of the workshop were to carry out a simulation of the project's two major outputs: the INDUSAC platform and the INDUSAC methodology. The workshop, attended by nine individuals - students, researchers, and representatives of companies - along with fourteen INDUSAC consortium partners guiding the test run, simulated the users' journeys through the INDUSAC platform, and tested the clarity of the methodology as envisioned by the INDUSAC project. The workshop also acquainted the users with the platform; collecting their feedback will serve as a guide to improve the beta version of the methodology (deliverable D1.4; Odic et al., 2023) in terms of simplification, streamlining, and additional necessary elements, resulting in a final version of the methodology (deliverable D1.6). Furthermore, the questions asked will also be used to populate the Frequently-Asked-Question section on the INDUSAC website.

II. THE WORKSHOP

1. Introduction, Context, and Goals of the Workshop

The workshop was organised as a Zoom event. During the opening session, the workshop was put into context of the INDUSAC project, the goals were outlined, and the agenda (Annex 1) was reviewed.

2. Putting the Platform in Perspective: Introduction to the INDUSAC Project

In the introductory session, the INDUSAC project was briefly described to the participants. The project consortium representing an international partnership was presented along with the general principles of the workflow of the project. The INDUSAC concept was described, including open calls, the concept of Challenges, co-creation projects, and Solutions. Emphasis was also put on the advantages of the project for participants. For students/researchers, this includes participation in international co-creation teams, collaborative experiences by working with students and researchers from different countries, access to and working with companies across the EU, solving real-life challenges, upskilling in transversal and entrepreneurial skills (communication, negotiation, results orientation, responsibility, creativity, planning, analytical thinking, among others), as well as getting financial compensation (students only), references, and a certificate of participation from INDUSAC. For researchers specifically, the advantages are: networking with students (in whom they may recognise potential new employees, such as young researchers) and joining in projects representing a first step towards possible larger future collaboration with companies. For companies, the advantages are: meeting ambitious young people from different countries, and obtaining solutions, all without any financial commitments on the company's side. Project partners responsible for promotion (WP4) will include these points in promotional material.

3. Introduction to the Methodology and the Miro Board

The workshop consisted of presentations followed by short sections dedicated to questions related to the presented methodology. The methodology of the project was presented visually as a schematic. Real-time feedback on the presentation of the INDUSAC methodology and platform was collected on the visual workspace, the Miro board, to which participants (including INDUSAC consortium members) were given the link, so as to facilitate real-time question-and-answer sessions, and discussion of any comments appearing on the board. Participants were shown how to write questions and comments on virtual post-its and drag-and-drop them to appropriate sections on the methodology schematic. The post-its were color-coded (green = congratulations on the process (not necessarily intended to include text), yellow = questions, blue = recommendation, red = missing information). Two separate schemes of the

methodology were prepared, one for companies and one for students/researchers, since their user journeys differ due to their roles in the project.

Following the introduction to the Miro board, the INDUSAC methodology, its stages and different components, were presented through schematic representations of user journeys for students/researchers (Figure 1), and separately for companies (Figure 2); after the explanation of each segment, participants were instructed to post their questions to that segment via the Miro board (Figures 3 and 4). Chronologically, the presentation of the user journey for students/researchers (Figure 1) was followed by posting questions (Figure 3), which was followed by the presentation of the user journey for companies (Figure 2), in turn followed by posting questions (Figure 4).

Figure 1 : Schematic representation of the INDUSAC methodology - user's journey for students/researchers (Source: the workshop presentation by partners from BAX).

Figure 2 : Schematic representation of the INDUSAC methodology - user's journey for companies (source: the workshop presentation by partners at BAX).

4. Interactive Guide through the Platform

Following the Miro-board-moderated discussion on the methodology, the INDUSAC platform was presented through a demonstration of a simulated workflow, for both students/researchers, and companies. A mock-up version of the INDUSAC platform was displayed via Zoom, and the individual steps in registering and navigating the platform, the user dashboard, and the process were shown on-screen, again separately for students/researchers and for companies. Participants were again instructed to post their questions via the Miro board (see Annex 2 for screenshots of posted questions – Figures 5 to 16). Chronologically, the presentation of the platform elements for students/researchers was followed by posting questions (Figures 5 to 10), which was followed by the presentation of the platform elements for companies, in turn followed by posting questions (Figures 11 to 16). As this document focuses on the methodology rather than the platform, further details regarding the elements and operation of the platform are beyond the scope of this deliverable.

5. Miro Board: Gathering Feedback

Questions arising during the presentations of the students'/researchers' and companies' user journeys were gathered in real-time through Miro board post-its (see Figures 3, 4 and Annex 2) and those collected during the platform simulation are shown more visibly in Annex 2.

INDUSAC Methodology - Students & Researchers

Figure 3 : Snapshot of the methodology schematics displayed on the Miro board, indicating questions/comments about students'/researchers' journey arising during the presentation (seen here as virtual post-its: green = congratulations on the process (not necessarily intended to include text), yellow = questions, blue = recommendation, red = missing information). Empty yellow (question) post-its reflect activity during the workshop from attendees who did not write questions but expressed them verbally during the discussion.

Figure 4 : Snapshot of the methodology schematics displayed on the Miro board, indicating questions/comments about companies' journey arising during the presentation (seen here as virtual post-its: green = congratulations on the process, yellow = questions, blue = recommendations, red = missing information). Empty yellow (question) post-its reflect activity during the workshop from attendees who did not write questions but expressed them verbally during the discussion.

All questions were addressed during the workshop. Most questions revolved around roles of, and expectations from, students, researchers, and companies, and around the selection and evaluation processes. The second-most frequently asked questions were related to the assembly of a co-creation team, the registration on the platform, writing Motivation Letters, and the duration and scheduling of the co-creation projects. Questions related to payments, certificates and IPR were least frequent. Some of the questions (see below) were readily answered during the presentation, as they were not addressing missing or unclear steps in the process, and required no additional modification of the proposed methodology. Others, such as the question of whether it is possible to apply with several Motivation Letters, but then cancel some of them in favour of others, deserved further discussion within the INDUSAC consortium (see Section 6). Certain questions concerned the functionality of the platform and as such do not affect the methodology in its present form. Despite being beyond the scope of this deliverable, for the sake of completion, the questions relevant to the platform are included in the question list below.

Questions extracted from the Miro board post-its that were clarified during the workshop and are to be included in the INDUSAC FAQ section:

- *As a student, how am I going to find others from different countries and form my team?*
- *Does the motivation letter have to follow a specific structure?*
- *Does the motivation letter have to be written in two languages?*
- *Do we have to create a project with a min./max. duration? What is the min./max. duration of a project?*
- *Group or individual motivation?*
- *By whom is the selection part/step done?*
- *What is the main goal for the researchers in participating in the project?*
- *How will students receive their payments?*
- *Will students receive any certificate from the project or from a university for their participation?*
- *Who approves the Solution?*
- *What happens if the Solution is not approved?*
- *What is the schedule and format for submitting Solutions?*
- *Is only the company providing assistance?*
- *What happens if a favourable Solution is not reached?*
- *(What happens if the project gives rise to) intellectual property? (What is the method of exploitation?)*
- *What is the difference between the “Evaluation of Solution” and “Evaluation and Feedback” phases?*
- *What if my study course is not included (in the registration form)?*
- *Is a diverse option possible? (*probably regarding the choice of gender)*
- *How do researchers fill in forms that ask for studies/universities etc.?*
- *What does the company expect?*
- *If I don't know anyone, how can I find people interested in the same Challenge as me?*
- *Can I initially apply for a team/search for members (presumably, prior to preparing a Motivation Letter)?*

Questions/recommendations from participants extracted from the Miro board post-its that **require discussion within the consortium**, and will be included in the FAQ section once the answers are clear; the answers will also be incorporated in the INDUSAC Methodology (Deliverable D1.6):

- *What do the companies have to do (during “project assistance”)?*
- *Clearly state the expectations from both sides (students/researchers on one side and companies on the other side)*
- *What are the terms for “project assistance” (e.g. number of meetings, communication tools, response time)?*
- *If I apply for multiple Challenges and just want to do one project but I get accepted for multiple ones, what do I do? Can I cancel one of them?*

Questions extracted from the Miro board post-its that **concern the INDUSAC platform**:

- *Is there one (Slack) channel per Challenge or is it all mixed?*
- *To form my team, how am I going to find other people’s emails so I can invite them?*
- *Is it possible to share the Motivation Letter as a PDF or Word document, which is easier to read, as opposed to reading on-screen?*

6. Lessons Learned: Suggestions for Improvements for the INDUSAC Methodology

The purpose of the methodology pre-validation report was to identify major unclear issues in order to evolve the methodology from its beta version (deliverable D1.4; Odic et al., 2023) to the first operational version. While most of the methodology appeared quite clear and/or was easily clarified during the workshop, two points were made during the methodology presentation that warrant a check if they are clearly explained in the beta version (reflected in the second group of questions above).

The first (contained in the first three questions, concerning project assistance) is the recommendation to make sure that expectations on the side of researchers/students as well as the side of companies are clear. Students/researchers need to be aware of the mentoring capabilities (level of expertise) that the companies have, and their scheduling capacities (for example, to be able to carry out a few meetings per project). As per the recommended co-creation project workflow, the company is expected to assist the co-creation team through consulting at certain key points (kick-off meeting, interim milestone meeting, final meeting) and answer the teams’ questions outside of these meetings, via e-mail / videocall / chat on the platform, to enable the functioning of the team between the meetings and enhance real co-creation. However, it should be made clear that the co-creation team is meant to carry out the task mostly independently. Specifics of the meeting dynamics are discussed between the company

and the co-creation team at their kick-off meeting. Likewise, the company needs to be aware of the skill level of the co-creation teams. The Challenge template includes the field where a company lists what it expects from the co-creation team. However, special attention could already be taken at the project promotion stage to make clear to all involved what to expect - for example, students should not expect full-time assistance from the companies whereas companies should not necessarily expect their Challenges to be solved by experts in the field but rather individuals who are there to learn the skills. This shall be discussed among partners responsible for WP1 as it concerns guidelines, but also partners responsible for WP4 as it should be included in promotional activities.

Second, a question of whether it is possible to apply with several Motivation Letters but then cancel some of them in favour of others deserves establishing a strong policy on the freedom of selecting Challenges to apply for. Thought should be put into discouraging too much speculation on the student's/researcher's part and encouraging them to prepare a single strong Motivation Letter rather than several less elaborated applications that could end up rejected and thus cost them a valuable opportunity (since the maximum number of Motivation Letters throughout all three cut-off dates is three). Cancellation of approved Motivation Letters from the co-creation team's side has not been explored in detail in the beta version of the methodology. This shall be discussed among partners responsible for WP1 as it concerns detailed guidelines in the calls.

In addition, a recommendation was given to include the promotion of the project into student curricula - project partners responsible for promotion (WP4) will be consulted on the possibilities of organising such an initiative.

7. FINAL REMARKS

Prior to the workshop, each member of the INDUSAC consortium invited individuals (students, researchers, companies) from focus groups previously involved in surveys and interviews regarding the industry-academia mechanism, to the event. The fairly low attendance (total of nine individuals) allowed for a controlled and manageable discussion, identified key questions to be resolved, and provided everyone (both the guests and members of the INDUSAC consortium) with an opportunity to elaborate on their questions on the Miro board.

8. CONCLUSIONS

The workshop, closing with the announcement that the platform goes live in October 2023, served several important purposes: it introduced, for the first time, the INDUSAC methodology and platform to individuals outside the INDUSAC consortium, and

through their input, gave invaluable insight into some of the elements that deserve additional attention, and are to be discussed within the project consortium. The questions and recommendations presented during the workshop will represent the basis for further improving and streamlining both the methodology and the platform for their optimal application and will also be included in the FAQ section.

III. LIST OF REFERENCES

Odic D., Mrgole U., Trobec M. (2023). Methodology beta version. Deliverable D1.4. in Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centered Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations (Horizon Europe project No. 101070297).

Odic D., Mrgole U., Trobec M. INDUSAC methodology. Deliverable D1.6. in Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centered Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations (Horizon Europe project No. 101070297). *Deliverable in preparation.*

IV. ANNEXES

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ANNEX 1 : The Workshop Agenda

15 September 2023, 9.00-11.00 am., ZOOM

09:00 - 09:05 Intro, context and goals of session (via PPT)

09:05 - 09:15 Intro to INDUSAC to put the platform in perspective (via PPT)

09:15 - 09:30 Introduce process and methodology with feedback gathered in Miro (via PPT and Miro)

09:30 - 10:15 Interactive guiding through the platform (consecutively students and then companies) and then let attendees play with mock ups themselves. Live feedback gathering in Miro (via Figma and Miro)

10:15 - 10:45 Joint discussion on feedback points (via Miro)

10:45 - 11:00 Closing, important conclusions, next steps and promotion of platform launch

ANNEX 2 : Screenshots of individual questions/comments

The screenshots below show questions/comments posted on the Miro board during the INDUSAC platform simulation. For clarity, in some images empty post-its (indicating either general satisfaction or non-existing questions) have been excluded.

The figure shows two screenshots of the INDUSAC sign-up process. The first screenshot shows a form with fields for 'List of study courses', 'Name', 'Family name', 'Address', 'Citizenship or residency', 'Gender', and 'E-mail'. A blue 'Next' button is at the bottom left, and '1/2' is at the bottom right. A yellow sticky note asks 'what if my study course is not included?'. A blue sticky note suggests 'it would be useful to specify the email (uni mail if applicable), you could receive notifications etc. via the mail.'. A second yellow sticky note asks 'is a diverse option possible?'. The second screenshot shows the 'Study Start' and 'Foreseen Study End' fields (Month and Year dropdowns) and a field for 'Name of public university where you study'. A yellow sticky note asks 'What about researchers here?'.

Figure 5 : Zoomed-in section of an individual step on the Miro board: Sign-up process for researchers and students.

The screenshot displays the INDUSAC website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, About, Open Calls, News&Events, Media, and Communication Toolkit, along with a Sign Up button. Below the navigation is a search bar and several filter buttons for Challenge Type, Organization, Country, and Industry. The main content area shows a grid of challenge cards, each with a title, description, and 'Read more'/'Apply' buttons. Two green sticky notes are placed on the right side of the grid, one over the top-right card and another over the bottom-right card.

Challenge 1: Selection of the equipment to support system for digitization of entire, natural, industrially processed animal leather in order t[...]
 6. Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)
 DigitalLeather doo
 Serbia
 Deadline at 31/01/2025

Challenge 2: Super Alloys
 In-space microgravity manufacturing of High Temperature Super Alloys
 8. Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain
 Mohit Joshi
 UK
 Deadline at 31/01/2025

Challenge 3: Cosmic Campaigns: Marketing the Future of Space Manufacturing
 3. Marketing campaign of the future
 Mohit Joshi
 UK
 Deadline at 31/01/2025

Challenge 4: Redesign and updating ENVIT's ReSoil® Website to Enhance Global Engagement and Accessibility
 4. Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis
 ENVIT, environmental engineering and technologies Ltd.
 EU MEMBER STATES
 Deadline at 30/01/2025

Challenge 5: New ideas to natural skincare marketing approaches
 3. Marketing campaign of the future
 ASYA GRAFY BIO INSITUTE d.o.o.
 Slovenia
 Deadline at 30/01/2025

Challenge 6: Creating New Business Service for Metalworking Industry
 9. Business model: Adding a service to my product - Building a PSS (product service system)
 Eurol d.o.o.
 Slovenia
 Deadline at 30/01/2025

Challenge 7: Abrasive Innovation: Crafting a Marketing Campaign of the Future for Metalworking Industry
 3. Marketing campaign of the future
 Eurol d.o.o.
 Slovenia
 Deadline at 30/01/2025

Challenge 8: Inovative custom made hardwood floors
 3. Marketing campaign of the future
 ALPOD d.o.o.
 Slovenia
 Deadline at 30/01/2025

Sticky Note 1: very good overview

Sticky Note 2: Really good interface and design

Figure 6 : Zoomed-in section of an individual step on the Miro board: Challenges for researchers and students.

Challenge in details

FOR IMPACT

A Fluidized Bed Riser Adsorption System For Selective Protein Recovery (FBRAS)

Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST)

From Luxembourg
Responsive
Innovative Products and Technologies

Summary Of The Technology

The invention proposes the development and testing of a novel unit operation, intended for the continuous sequestration of valuable bio-products (including proteins) from a complex feedstock. The system can help to integrate the bio-manufacturing scenario by introducing a novel unit operation that is able to simultaneously remove biomass, selectively capture the product of interest, and concentrate such product. Moreover, the proposed technology can operate in continuous mode, therefore helping to intensify downstream operations. The integration and intensification paradigm results in higher:

what does the company expect?

Details Of The Technology Offer

Companies within the biomanufacturing sector are constantly looking for novel products and to gain a competitive edge on the market by continuously improving on their production processes; this helps to distinguish themselves from their competitors in an ever-increasing competitive landscape. Manufacturers of industrial, specialty and pharmaceutical proteins are reporting capacity constraints due to improvements in the product levels currently attainable via fermentation. The invention proposes the development and testing of a novel unit operation, intended for the continuous sequestration of valuable bio-products (including proteins) from a complex feedstock. The system can help to integrate the bio-manufacturing scenario by introducing a novel unit operation that is able to simultaneously remove biomass, selectively capture the product of interest, and concentrate such product. Moreover, the proposed technology can operate in continuous mode, therefore helping to intensify downstream operations. The integration and intensification paradigm results in higher:

Benefits:

The FBRAS technology has the advantage of being placed directly, for example, after fermentation or cell disruption (i.e., in case of intracellular proteins), creating savings in required equipment and manufacturing time, and decreasing contamination and degradation risks. The system incorporates individual contactors for "columns" for each stage of operation (e.g., product capture and biomass removal, adsorbent washing, product recovery or "elution", and adsorbent regeneration). The design provides more flexibility in adjusting process conditions and less dependency of the various operational steps on each other in comparison to the mechanically sophisticated column arrangements required in periodic counter current chromatography (PCC) or simulated moving bed (SMB) chromatography. The FBRAS technology is positioned towards manufacturers of industrial.

Send a request for information to Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST)

Submit motivation letter

By clicking "Submit motivation letter" you are signing up on Innoportal.com and accepting our "Terms of Service and Privacy policy"

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Help

Need help requesting additional information or have questions regarding this Technology Offer? [Contact Research Luxembourg support](#)

FAQs

- How do I write a winning proposal?
- Who will evaluate my proposal?
- How do I protect my intellectual property?
- Do I have to reveal confidential information?
- Do I need to sign a non-disclosure agreement (NDA) before submitting my proposal?
- How long will it take to get a response?
- What happen if I am elected?
- What happen if I am not elected?

Figure 7 : Zoomed-in section of an individual step on the Miro board: Challenge in details for researchers and students. The green (congratulations) post-it is empty as it is not necessarily intended to include text).

Forming a team

The screenshot shows a user profile for Taras Zaiachuk (UI/UX Designer, joined February 14, 2023) on the left. The main content area is titled "Team" and contains three challenge cards for forming a team:

- Challenge 1:** "Form Your Team for Challenge: A Fluidized Bed Riser Adsorption System for Selective Protein Recovery...". It shows a list of participants: debble.baker@example.com (Sent), Darrell Steward (Accepted), and Kathryn Murphy (Rejected). There is a "Send invite" button and a "+ Add" button.
- Challenge 2:** "Form Your Team for Challenge: Equipment For The Compression Of Fluids Using Thermal Energy". It shows four empty "Send invite" buttons and a "+ Add" button.
- Challenge 3:** "Form Your Team for Challenge: APTAMER : Small Single-Stranded Nucleic Acid (DNA Or RNA) For Virus...". It shows four empty "Send invite" buttons and a "+ Add" button.

Three yellow sticky notes are placed over the interface with the following text:

- Sticky Note 1 (top left): "to form my team, how I'm going to find other people emails so I can invite them?"
- Sticky Note 2 (top right): "if i dont know anyone, how can i find people interested in the same challenge as me?"
- Sticky Note 3 (bottom right): "Can I initially apply for a team/ search for members?"

At the bottom of the team management section, there is a "Save changes" button.

Figure 8 : Zoomed-in section of an individual step on the Miro board: Forming a team.

Submit a motivation

There should be no need to fill in the Team ID. This should be linked to the overview before where the Teams are shown linked to specific challenges

Seeking the way of improving the rheological characteristics of soy lecithin

Posted by Anonymous Organization · Responsive · Specific Technical Innovation · Project Size Range : 50,000 - 250,000 € · Deadline at 22/12/2023 · EMEA

Save draft
Submit Motivation

Attachments

Drag & Drop your files here

Please upload your resume and, if needed, further documents concerning your idea for a solution.
Possible formats: PDF, JPG, DOC, AVI, MPG4, XLS

Add your team mates here use one field for each member:

Please be aware that the motivation will only be processed after submission, if all linked team members confirm their participation. An automated e-mail will be sent to every team member after you submit the motivation.

@yourself 0/50	@teammate 1 0/50
@teammate 2 0/50	@teammate 3 0/50
@teammate 4 0/50	@teammate 5 0/50

+

Technology Calls on posted and managed well as evaluation of is the trusted open innovation science network aimed at directly connect industry needs with professionals online.

If I apply for multiple challenges and just want to do one project but I get accepted for multiple ones, what do I do? Can I cancel one of them?

I believe that the maximum words limit in each box should be less. It will take much time for the teams to complete this step. More detailed info can be applied to the company directly after the selection

does it have to be two languages on one page?

Figure 9 : Zoomed-in section of an individual step on the Miro board: Submit a motivation.

Submit a Solution

Seeking the way of improving the rheological characteristics of soy lecithin
Posted by Anonymous Organization · Responsive · Specific Technical Innovation · Project Size Range: \$0.000 - 250.000 € · Deadline at 22/12/2022 · EMEA

[Save draft](#) [Submit Solution](#)

Attachments

Drag & Drop your files here
Please upload your resume and if needed further documents concerning your idea for a solution.
Possible formats: PDF, JPG, DOC, AVI, MP4, FLV

Add your team mates here use one field for each member* How does this field work?

Please be aware that in evaluation it is only the proposal after submission. If all listed team members confirm their participation, an automated e-mail will be sent to every team member after you submit the evaluation.

@yourname1	0/100	@teammate 1	0/100
@teammate 2	0/100	@teammate 3	0/100
@teammate 4	0/100	@teammate 5	0/100

Taxes, start writing the title of your Challenge*

Identify your motivation letter with a self-explanatory title

¿Qué es Lorem Ipsum?

Lorem Ipsum es simplemente el texto de relleno de las imprentas y archivos de texto. Lorem Ipsum ha sido el texto de relleno estándar de las industrias desde el año 1500, cuando un impresor (N. del T. persona que se dedica a la imprenta) desconocido usó una galería de textos y los mezcló de tal manera que logró hacer un libro de textos especímenes. No solo sobrevivió 500 años, sino que también ingresó como texto de relleno en documentos electrónicos, quedando esencialmente igual al original. Fue popularizado en los 60s con la creación de las hojas "Letraset", las cuales contenían párrafos de Lorem Ipsum, y más recientemente con software de autoselección, como por ejemplo Aldus PageMaker, el cual incluye versiones de Lorem Ipsum.

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Library of Resources

- Document 1
- Document 2
- Document 3

About you

Your complete profile will be included with your solution proposal. Review your information below:

Taras Zalachuk
UI/UX Designer · Ukraine
Expert in Electronics, IT and Telecommunications. Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies, Industrial Technologies and AI more... [Add more](#)
Email address: taras@uigmail.com
Phone number: [Add phone number](#) [Show phone number](#)
Manager profile: <https://www.innovat.org/cv/ta-zalachuk>
Your complete profile will be included with your application. [Update your profile](#)

The team ID I think is not intuitive, maybe it could be better to have a roll-up with your differents groups and you could what you want for that challenge

Figure 10 : Zoomed-in section of an individual step on the Miro board: Submit a solution.

Sign up process

Sign Up to INDUSAC
Quick challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation mechanism for industry-academia collaborations

List of NACE codes:

Name of the company*

Address of the company

Country: Number of employees:

Name of legal representative

VAT number: ID number:

Web page

Name of contact person

E-mail of contact person

Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community (NACE codes)

[Create an account](#)

I confirm that all the data is correct and that I can provide written proof. If required from INDUSAC partners, European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HDCA), European Commission, European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), Court of Auditors (ECA) or other competent EU institutions.

Figure 11 : Zoomed-in section of an individual step on the Miro board: Sign-up process for companies. The green (congratulations) post-its are empty as they are not necessarily intended to include text).

Publish PCAs

Post your Challenge

How you write and describe your challenge is as crucial as what you are seeking for. Find below a variety of templates to guide you through writing your challenge

What do you want to offer?

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis

Finding white spots in the product portfolio
Development of an action-plan for relevant clusters based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio and the clustering of the product portfolios elements

Marketing campaign of the future
Design of a campaign based on a market analysis with focus on customers and trend analysis.

Meet the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis
Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Personal)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Personas, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

E-Commerce and Digital Services (Basis Scenarios)
Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple Trends/ Scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

Business plan - reduce your risk and optimize your planning
The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain
Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

Business model: Adding a service to my product - Building a PSS
The development of new business models for a given product.

Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
Future-oriented development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

Long description of PCA - more information about increments and in general list of increments

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Scenario/Trend analysis and references (e.g., Word)
- Catalogue of future robust product properties (e.g., Excel)

Project process description: Kick-off meeting, regular meetings from team, milestone meetings after product properties, final meeting! (illustrated as Gantt Chart: Phase 1, Milestone, Phase 2.)

Title for your Challenge:

Minimum 30 characters

Publish

Save Draft

Manage posts

Slack Channel
should be
generated and
inserted
automatically

Figure 12 : Zoomed-in section of an individual step on the Miro board: Publish PCAs. The green (congratulations) post-its are empty as they are not necessarily intended to include text).

Figure 13 : Zoomed-in section of an individual step on the Miro board: Company dashboard. The empty yellow (question) post-it reflects activity during the workshop from attendees who did not write questions but expressed them verbally during the discussion.

Company Dashboard: Motivation letter

Go Back to My Posts

The power of microalgae for BHT replacement and sustainable innovations
 Motivation Letter 16 submitted to your technology call: Seeking Natural Antioxidants Coming From Microalgae To Replace BHT in Personal Care Products

[Previous Motivation Letter](#) [Next Motivation Letter](#)

Leslie Alexander
 Scientist
 From European Union · Reception Date: **2023-05-27** · Lead Qualification Status: **New**

[✗ Reject Motivation Letter](#) [💬 Send a message](#) [👁️ View Leslie's Profile](#) [📄 View Contact Details](#)

Description

In recent years, industries have been committed to developing sustainable products to meet market trends linked to consumer demands for natural beauty and personal care products that are safe and respectful of biodiversity and the environment. Due to their immense biodiversity and unique metabolic pathways, microalgae are biological sources of innovative and sustainable molecules with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antiviral properties. Some of these natural molecules can replace the use of synthetic antioxidant ingredients. Indeed, it was shown that some microalgae extracts exhibited higher antioxidant activity than BHT [1]. Alganelle unlocks the potential of microalgae to be competitive photosynthetic cell factories for efficient production of recombinant products through its disruptive technology and its rare know-how in synthetic biology and biomanufacturing.

Stage of development

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So much text, is not better to read a PDF, maybe you could share a document PDF, WORD, and they could read it easy than in web (from my point of view)

Figure 14 : Zoomed-in section of an individual step on the Miro board: Company dashboard: Motivation Letter. The empty yellow (question) post-it reflects activity during the workshop from attendees who did not write questions but expressed them verbally during the discussion.

Motivation letter: Reject & Acceptance

Figure 15 : Zoomed-in section of an individual step on the Miro board: Motivation letter: Reject & Acceptance for companies. The empty yellow (question) post-it reflects activity during the workshop from attendees who did not write questions but expressed them verbally during the discussion.

View Team

Figure 16 : Zoomed-in section of an individual step on the Miro board: View Team for companies. The green (congratulations) post-its are empty as they are not necessarily intended to include text).

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